

English Language Teachers should teach Students how to Write their Names

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Abstract: Names are universal phenomena common to all known societies. However, every culture has its own naming practices and the sequence which the names should be arranged. There are observed name-identity crises people experience in various institutions in Nigeria. This is associated with inconsistency in name pattern which ranges from, omission of some letters from names, wrong spelling of name, change of name without an official backup, to a wrong way of introducing oneself in an official setting. These have deprived most Nigerians a lot of good opportunities within Nigeria and outside Nigeria. This work analyzed the inconsistency in name pattern and proposed that “name presentations” should be included in the curriculum of the Use of English, from primary to tertiary levels so as to ensure that students are taught how to write their names and introduce themselves officially in a way that is globally acceptable.

Keywords: *Name, Name presentations, Inconsistency, Curriculum, Use of English.*

INTRODUCTION

Name is a universal phenomenon common to all known societies. Names can be viewed as semantic labels that serve to both identify an individual and differentiate them from others. (Watzlawik, et al. 2016). However, every culture has its own naming practice.

Our interactions with respondents revealed that much importance is not placed on the phenomenon of name patterns. Most people do not know the implications of not maintaining a particular name pattern until it is dawn on them. The name-identity crisis has limited lot of people from achieving their goals in life, it has limited their competition both within the country and at the international space. The name-identity crises however, was traceable to the fact that the pattern of the cultural name sequence that existed in Nigeria in the pre-colonial era is totally different from the Caucasian system that was accepted officially. The Caucasian system is alien to Nigerian cultural practices, hence, addressing this challenge has therefore become necessary. How do we remedy the situation becomes an objective. In order to prevent the future generations from experiencing problems arising from inconsistent name patterns, it is proposed that the topic ‘presentation of names’ should be incorporated into the Use of English curriculum at all levels of education, from primary school to the university. Students should be taught how to write their names and introduce themselves officially in a way that is globally acceptable as a topic in Use of English. The focus in this work is on Yoruba, Igbo, Hausa, Efik and Ibibio.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Identify the name patterns patterns of name sequence

Why is it necessary to teach students how to write their names?

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The specific objectives of this study are to:

- i. identify the name patterns across culture in Nigeria
- ii identify presentation of names in writing and physical/oral introduction in official settings .
- iii. provide suggestions on presentation of names and physical/oral introduction in official settings.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative research methodology in data collection and analysis. This consists of a participatory observer methodology, literature consultation, and conducting an oral interview with elderly men who are native speakers of Hausa, Igbo, Yoruba and Efik/Ibibio. The Yoruba speakers consist of a Professor of Linguistics at the Department of Linguistics and Languages, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba Akoko, Ondo State and a Senior Lecturer of Yoruba oral literature at the Department of Nigerian Languages Education, Lagos State University of Education, Epe, Lagos. The Igbo speakers consist of a 75years old man from Orumba North Local Government Area of Anambra State and an 83 years old man from Agwu Local Government Area of Enugu state. The Hausa speakers consist of a 72years old man from Kaduna State and an 84years old man from Sokoto State. The Efik speakers are 64 and 89 years old men, both from Nsit-Ibium Local Government Area of Akwa-Ibom State. A random selection and interview of some elites on their opinions on name-identity crises was also done. The respondents were only males because name pattern in Nigeria is associated with patrilineal patronymic culture. The men are the custodians of the culture and have more information on the local history of naming.

Name Pattern Before Western Influence

Personal naming practices are significant aspects of different cultures around the world, with traditions, patterns and conventions differing from one society to another. Such names often serve as subtle reference to people's history, traditions and cultural heritage (Mensah 2021). In the precolonial era, many Nigerian ethnic groups did not use surnames in the way they arunderstood in Western context as there existed the case of biological trajectory. Names were often tied to personal attributes or circumstances of the birth of the child and thereafter sur-named by tracing the child to the family lineage, clan, ancestors or notable professions, loca-tion and the child's parentage, and also, the tribe or ethnic heritage. The following are in-stances of the Hausa, Igbo, Yoruba, Efik and Ibibio cases.

Traditional Hausa names in the precolonial era were largely referential in nature. The prefix "Dan" means "Son of". For instance, "Dangote" translates as "Son of Gote", "Dantata" as "son of Tata" and "Danmaigoro" as "son of Maigoro". Names were often given based on the circumstances surrounding child's birth, such as the day of the week, season, physical charac-teristics, time of birth, family or community situation, or lineage, etc. However, the arrival of Islam in Northern Nigeria led to a significant cultural transformation, as the society increas-ingly aligned with Islamic principles, which became the dominant ideology. Also, this shift

intensified during the Sokoto Jihad of 1804 brought about a major transformation in which, many of the indigenous cultural practices of the time were replaced with those that were purely Islamic (Muhammad 2023). Consequently, there was a growing preference for Islamic names” (Adamu, 2020, p. 13 as cited in Muhammad 2023). Influenced by religious beliefs, it became customary among the Hausa to name individuals after the prophet mentioned in the Qur’an and also, after companions of the Prophet Muhammad, a practice that has remained prevalent for generations. Therefore, the prefix “Dan” meaning “son of” was replaced with ‘ibn’ meaning “son of” and “bint” meaning “daughter of”, in Arabic language as written in the Quran. Hence, for instance, “Abdulrahman ibn Mohammed” means “Abdulrahman” (the name of the child) son of “Mohammed” (the father of the child). The adopted naming system is the more reason we see cases of many ‘Mohammed’ in the same work place and they will not be in any way related. However, when children were dispatched to schools from their villages in batches, the name of their community will be added to their names in order to differentiate them. For example, Sheu Shagari, Aminu Tambuwal, Abdul Ningi, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa, etc. (this is not an established fact, but our respondent gave them as examples).

The Igbos usually take their names from the gods ‘chi’ which an individual or family serves, as well as from the circumstances surrounding the child’s birth, thereafter, they refer to the father’s name and the clan, the occupation or profession of the family or ancestral lineage. Eze (2020), asserts that some of these surnames include the events such as the market days, deities, festivals, titles, and other elements of the community life. An example is in “Chinedu nwa Mazi/Ije Ikenna Okoro Olomalu” kindred” which means ‘Chinedu’ the son of Mr or Chief Ikenna, son of Mr Okoro from Olumalu kindred.

This Igbo pattern of naming was obtainable in Efik/Ibibio before a more interesting patronymic structure began. Shortly after the colonization, there used to be a general family lineage surname given to the child as an identity with the family (like it is applicable with the Yoruba ethnic group till date). Although, this still existed until around late 1970s in some parts but it is almost gone into extinction. (According to our informants, what changed the order is a bit difficult to pin down). The order of giving a child the general family name changed to a particular structural pattern, a surname of the child will be his/her grandfather’s personal name (whether English or native), followed by his/her father’s personal name (whether English or native) and then, his/her own personal name (whether English or native). The more reason a child can have English names all through or a particular name appear twice in the child’s name, as in ‘Eyo Akpan Eyo’. In this case, the personal name of his grandfather is ‘Eyo’, while his father’s personal name is ‘Akpan’ and his own name is also ‘Eyo’. When he grows to having his own child, his grandfather’s name (the first Eyo) would have gone, his child picks his father’s name ‘Akpan’ (who is now the grandfather to the new born) as his surname, his own name (the second Eyo) as his first name, followed by the new born’s personal name which will be in the form of ‘Akpan Eyo Gabriel’. When ‘Gabriel’ has his own child, ‘Akpan’ drops, the name of the new born becomes ‘Eyo Gabriel (the new name)’. In essence, this special and interesting patrilineal sequence of naming and a common practice among the Efik/Ibibio as of today is grandfather’s name (surname), father’s name (first name), and given name (middle name).

In the Yoruba naming tradition, names were given to the child based on the circumstances surrounding the child's birth such as the baby's physical condition, posture at delivery, birth order or notable events occurring at the time. In addition, a child may be given a praise name, commonly referred to as 'oruko oriki'. After which the child will be surnamed tracing him/her to the parentage which include the mother's name followed by the occupation or the cultural heritage of the father. A girl's name can be in the following order - Ajoke, omo Asake, omo Bamdele Ajikojusogun ti ilu Ilorin Afonja. This means, Ajoke (a praise name given to a female child meaning 'a child meant to be taken care of by all'), child of Asake 'mother's name', child of Bamidele (the father) of Ajikojusogun 'the lineage of warriors' of Ilorin 'the capital of Kwara State'. Another example is, Ojo, omo Olayemi, omo Ayantunji, omo Eruowa, omo Obokun, Ijesha omo obokun. This means, Ojo (a male child who was born with his umbilical cord tied around his neck), child of Olayemi (mother's name), child of Ayantunji (father's name, from the lineage of drummers) from Ijesha, a town in Osun State.

As observed, traditional African communities shared similar traits and parallel intricate values in their naming system. The pattern of surname that existed before colonization was referential; in the form of "(the child's name) son/daughter of ...", a child will be traced to his/her family lineage, clan, ancestor, deity, or family profession in the village of his/her ethnic group. This reflects who they are and as well where they are coming from. According to one of our respondents, "the use of the referential expression 'son of' serves an important purpose. It reflects the idea that while members of the community may not always know the child's father (he may have travelled since he was a child), they are more likely to recognize the child's grandfather or the lineage and kindred to which the child belongs. However, the cultural diversity in Africa has been further reinforced by the extensive spread of missionary religions such as Christianity and Islam, both of which have introduced their own distinct cultural influences into existing indigenous traditions (Igboin, 2014).

The English Naming System

In English naming conventions, for instance, British names are traditionally patrilineal. Every individual inherits their surname (also known as the 'last name') from their father's family name, (although, this is not an enforced custom). The first name, also known as the 'personal or given name' is assigned at birth and serves as an individual identifier. It always precedes the family name which is inherited and shared with all other members of the immediate family. Typically, all paternal relatives including sons, fathers, grandfathers and great-great grandfathers, have the same surname. Many British also have a 'middle name', which is a secondary given name written between the person's first name and their family name, (although, middle names are optional and are rarely used in daily life). However, most British have one or multiple middle names. According to Evason (2021), there is a pattern to which the arrangement of names follow in British English. For instance, the first given name, followed by the middle given name(s), and then, the family name (surname). Meanwhile, in some instances, parents may choose to combine their family names, including that of the father and the mother. In this kind of instance, their children will have a hyphenated surname, for example; Bryan Adams-Smith. In this example, 'Bryan' is the personal name, while 'Adams-Smith' is the surname. Also, it is traditional for women to adopt their husband's

family name at marriage, however, this practice is declining and less of a cultural requirement. (Evason, 2021).

Nigerian Naming Convention After Colonization

The official use of surnames in Nigeria started during the British colonial administration in the late 19th century to the mid-20th century (source: oral interview). The colonial administration however required a standard naming conventions for the purpose of keeping records and all other legal purposes. This made Nigerians adopt surnames derived from their father's name or clan, this is most evident in the patrilineal ethnic groups. This practice continued even after the independence in 1960, surname became an essential part of Nigerian naming practices, and of course, an integral part of their identity. As noted in Ibemesi (2011) and Ogbonna (1972), the adoption of surnames and inherited family names became widespread and essentially mandatory in Igbo society during the twentieth century, largely due to the introduction of formal education and white-collar jobs.

Meanwhile, during the colonial administration, some Nigerians were converted to Christianity, and this led to the addition of a baptismal English names and the emergence of a plurality of names given to individuals. The father's family name, followed by the personal native name of the child which usually revolves around the circumstances surrounding his/her birth, and the baptismal name. For the Muslims, the father's family name, followed by the Islamic name of the child and then the personal native name. In the traditional religion, names are given in this same order according to the inspirations from the gods.

The Teaching of Name Sequence Officially in Nigeria

As observed in official places, for example, banks, embassy, immigration office, employment offices, etc., quite a number of people usually cry or feel disturbed because of losing juicy opportunities due to minor mistakes of incorrect sequence of names or inconsistencies in name pattern. A woman observed in the bank cried profusely because she was deprived access to withdraw money which she needed urgently from her account because of a mistake in her name pattern. The banker told her that her account name has just two names, her surname and the first name, instead of three names - surname, first name and the other name. The woman argued that she had never written three names since she was in the primary school till adulthood, she had always adhere with the two names – surname and her name which her father used to enroll her in the primary school. However, it is understandable that her father may not be informed, but if she had been enlightened, she would not have made such mistake.

Another scenario was the case of a young man of 22 years who had been struggling to gain admission into a university. He missed the opportunity again due to the fact that, the name on his O'level credentials is different from the one on his Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) registration. He had Okoro Kelechukwu Jude on his O'level results, while on his UTME, he had Patrick Jude. Claiming that he adopted Patrick Jude because he preferred to be addressed only by English names. He picked his father's baptismal name, and joined it with his own baptismal name. This, however, earned him a disqualification! This practice is rampant among the young people of this age and time as many of them want to associate completely with the western culture. Some, because of their religious belief that their destiny is

tied to their name, change their ancestral surnames to their father's first or middle name. According to Eze (2020:64), a major concern is that children and young people no longer adopt the traditional family names commonly shared among blood relatives. Instead, they increasingly use their father's personal or foreign names, particularly baptismal names, a trend he considers harmful to the Igbo nation". In contrast though, Ayantayo (2010 cited in Igboin, 2024), rejects the idea that names determine an individual's life outcomes. He argues that, there is no "logical relationship between the name a person bears and the fortunes they experience in life".

Another compelling instance reported by Joanna Oyeleke in the Tribune newspaper on August 20, 2022, highlights the consequences of inconsistent name usage. It involved the disqualification of the APC Governor-elect of Bayelsa State, David Lyon, in the November 16, 2019 governorship election, which stemmed from the discrepancies of names on the credentials of his Deputy Governor-elect, Biobarakuma Deji-Eriemienyo. For example, his primary school leaving certificate bore the name 'Adeyi-Eremienyo', while his GCE certificate carried 'Deji-Eremienyo'. These inconsistencies in his name, along with other issues identified by the court, ultimately led to the nullification of their electoral victory.

From our findings, over 80% of our respondents have found themselves in a name dilemma of one case or the other, it is either a change in the order of names, incomplete or incorrect name, etc. The best way to overcome the problem of which some people have already done is to swear a court affidavit to the effect of change of name. How then can we prevent the future generation from falling into this kind of dilemma is what we shall examine under "the use of English and name ordering".

The Use of English and Name Ordering

The importance of maintaining consistency in name patterns cannot be overemphasized, as a name serves as a key marker of identity and must be handled with precision. Although, the western style of name arrangement is commonly adopted, the multiple names often given to individuals in this region require careful management due to the risks associated with inconsistencies in name patterns (Tribune newspaper reported on 20th August, 2022 by Joanna Oyeleke). There are a lot of confusion on the pattern which names should be arranged and also, how personalities can introduce themselves physically/orally in official settings.

How Should Names Be Written

1. Students need to be educated on the proper order of names accepted in the country. In Nigeria, for example, official documentation typically requires the surname to be written first, followed by the individual's first name and then other names.

For instance: Ademola Adeyemi Anthony
 (Surname) (First name) (Other name)

It is important for individuals to become familiar with this format and use it consistently across all records, including birth certificates, primary six to O'level exams registrations, as well as essential documents such as NIN, BVN, voter's card, international passport, driver's license, and other official records. Some of our respondents were victims of inconsistency in

the pattern of names arrangement. In one document, it is Adeyemi Ademola Anthony, while in another, it is Ademola Anthony Adeyemi. It is important for teachers to educate their students on maintaining a strict compliance to this particular order or pattern.

2. Teachers should stop the habit of asking school age student “What is your father’s name?”. The correct question is “What is your surname?”. A lot of students give their father’s name as surname when asked the question wrongly and this poses challenges on the name and identity of the child in the future.

3. Students should be taught to avoid errors in the spelling of their names. We encounter different cases such as:

- i. Incorrect spelling of names. Cases such as “Charles written as “Charlse”, “Joseph” as “Joshep”, “Cephas” as “Cefas”, etc.

Also, there are cases of substituting /r/ and /l/ in Igbo. For example; “Obiageli” written as “Obiageri”, “Amarachi” as “Amalachi” etc. The users of names such as these claim the names are the same when they encounter issues. The interchangeability of /r/ and /l/ in Igbo language is an understandable linguistic phenomenon, but consistency is required in filling important documents. If you are using /r/, then be consistent with it and vice-versa.

- ii. Incorrect spelling of names in cases of omission. For example, “Folagbade” written as “Folagade”, “Omotosho” as “Omotoso”, “Akadiri” as “Akadri”, “Bakare” as “Bakre”, “Sandejiwa” as “Sandewa”, “Ayinde” as Ainde”, “Akinbiire” as “Abiire”, etc.
- iii. Incorrect spelling of names in cases of addition. For example, a Yoruba man who was given an Arabic name “Ismail” and it is this same “Ismail” he has on his NIN, then goes to the bank to fill in “Ismaila”, “Quadri” as “Quadiri” or “Kadiri”, etc.
- iv. Incomplete spelling of names is the case of omissions. For example, somebody’s name on the NIN ID Card is Adebambo Oluwaseyi Ezekiel, and then on the WAEC result is Adebambo Oluseyi Ezekiel. This person, when registering for WAEC omitted “wa” in “Oluwaseyi” thinking it is still the same. Or someone who is an Igbo whose name on the birth certificate is “Tochukwu” or “Obiageli” but filled “Tochi” or “Oby” on all other documents. Semantically, these names are the same but in writing, it is unacceptable. Some people will even remove the prefix of their names such as the Yoruba names: “Olasehinde” will be registered as “Sehinde”, “Oluwafemi” as “Femi”. Also, in baptismal or English names such as “Elizabeth” written as “Lizzy”, “Emmanuel” as “Emma”, “Alexander” as “Alex”, “Theodore” as “Theo”, “Natasha” written as “Nat” or “Tasha”, etc.

4. Students that have multiple of names should be guided to consistently use the ones recorded by their parents in official documents. For example, within the Yoruba naming tradition, it is customary for various individuals such as parents, grandparents, extended family members, and even family friends, to give names to a child during the naming ceremony. As a

result, a Yoruba child may have five to six names. However, over time, one of these names often becomes the commonly used form of address. Ultimately, (although, not in all cases), the biological parents usually determine the name that the child adopts for official purposes (Appiah, 2010). Therefore, teachers should ensure that students are familiar with and consistently use the specific names documented by their parents in formal records.

Additionally, discrepancies in the spelling of names across identification documents can also be regarded as a form of inconsistency in name usage. It is important for teachers to ensure that students learn how to spell their names correctly, this may even be given as a continuous assessment question. For instance, a particular senior professor in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan, whose name was usually written badly by students had to add “What is the name of the lecturer teaching this course?” as a compulsory question in the semester exam. Hence, no student passed through the department without spelling his name correctly. This culture can be adopted by teachers, “write your name in full” should be a compulsory question in either the CA or exam and corrections will be made for those that have deficiency. By this, students would have mastered the spellings of their names correctly and the particular order it should be arranged in all of their documents.

5. Make all changes in the name official: all corrections to names should be made through official procedures. It is important that individuals who have irregularity in their name pattern and those saddled with certain needs that require a change in name, follow the appropriate legal process. In Nigeria, this typically involves obtaining a court affidavit and subsequently publishing the change in a newspaper. Copies of the newspaper in which the change is announced then serve as proof in case any issue concerning name discrepancies arise in the future.

The Physical/Oral Introduction in Official Settings

The dated back confusion of the phrase “my names are” is appalling. A lot of students still make the mistake till date. It is unquestionable nonstandard by the conventions of modern English. The findings of Kperogi (2011) suggest that this style of conversational self-reference is mainly found in Nigerian and Kenyan English. He proposes that it may be a remnant of older British English that has persisted in some former British colonies, as modern native English speakers no longer introduce themselves in that manner.

When introducing oneself in modern English, it is not right to say “my names are”. The number of words in a person’s name collectively projects one’s identity whether it has just one word or more. This is likened to saying the title of a book, if we cannot say “the titles of the books are”, then it is not right to say “my names are”. Just like a person’s name, the title of a book consists of several words, but we do not pluralize the title of a book because of the number of words it is made up of. “Name” in the sense of its use, is a singular noun phrase or a collective noun. It is a linguistic unit that can refer either to a person’s first name alone or to the combination of their first, middle and last names. Therefore, the socially accepted and grammatically correct way to introduce oneself is by saying “My name is Adeyemi” or “My name is Adeyemi Anthony Ademola.” Even when additional names such as “Anthony” and

“Ademola” are included, the word name remains singular and does not require pluralization or a plural verb form.

1. Choose only one title: The use of titles such as ‘Miss’ or ‘Mrs’ along with other titles such as ‘Dr Mrs’ or ‘Pastor Dr’, ‘Prophet Prof.’ is grammatically wrong. In a society like Nigeria, people do this to flaunt achievements and obsession with titles. We should learn to introduce ourselves rightly in this order, “I am Mrs A..., a medical doctor by profession or I am pastor O, a professor of Applied Linguistics”, or simply say “I am Dr or Professor A...”. Or, when writing, Mrs Adeolu Jakande (PhD), Pst Oriola Olufunbi (PhD), or Dr Adeolu Jakande, Dr Oriola Olufunbi, etc.
2. Writing a professorial prefix in publication: When writing scientific papers to international journals;
 - i. The arrangement of name should be in the reverse order of how we introduce ourselves. For instance, the proper introduction of oneself is in the order of ‘my name is Ademola Adeyemi Anthony’, while in publication, it should be in the order of ‘Adeyemi Anthony Ademola’. The writer should write his/her first name first, followed by the middle name (if any), and then, the name that comes last is the last name/surname. Surname should come last and that is why it is usually referred to as the last name in some institutions.
 - ii. Another style is to write the surname in capital followed by the first and middle names in normal cases – ADEEMOLA Adeyemi Anthony. Note that no comma is required after the surname in capital.
 - iii. Another style also, is to write the surname first, followed by a comma and then the other names (all the names in this case should be written in normal case). For example: Ademola, Adeyemi Anthony.

All these cases allow the science editors the ease of alphabetical tracing in publication.

CONCLUSION

The importance of name pattern and presentation was established as they appear in key documents, such as in birth certificates, important examinations from the primary school stage to employment. Inconsistencies were identified across culture in name pattern, while potential problems and confusions pervaded presentation of names and physical/oral introduction in official settings. Students should therefore be educated on the risks associated with inconsistencies in name usage and the importance of maintaining a consistent name pattern to avoid disappointment and embarrassment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the discrepancies both in writing and oral presentation of the names, the following recommendations are made:

- i The concept of name patterns should be included in the teacher training curriculum.
- ii At every training sessions, seminars and workshops for teachers, and conferences, the sensitization on concept of naming patterns should be done for old teachers
- iii Teaching of names or presentation of name should be incorporated into the course content of

Use of English in the tertiary institutions, and the curriculum of primary and secondary schools.

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